

Kinetics and Mechanism of Phototemplate Polymerization of Methylacrylate

SANJAY K. AWASTHI and A. K. SRIVASTAVA*

Department of Chemistry, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002

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The template photopolymerization of methylacrylate (MA) along with syndiotactic polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA, $\bar{M}_v=110000$) at 30° in dimethylformamide (DMF) has been studied to examine the effect of the concentration and average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of template. [monomer] and [initiator] upon the kinetics and mechanism. Viscometric measurement showed that complexation between PMMA and PMA was maximum when the template-polymer ratio was 1 : 1 and the time required for complete complexation was about 8 min. The overall energy of activation (E_a) was 84.0 and 115.0 kJ mol⁻¹ in the presence and absence of PMMA respectively.

In template polymerization we seek to achieve polymerization of monomer units attached to a template in a predetermined manner and to synthesise polymers or copolymer having precise structure and microstructures complementary to those of the template¹.

In the present work, we report the photopolymerization of methyl acrylate in presence of atactic polymethyl methacrylate with a predominance of syndiotactic sequence, as template at 30° for 270 min.

Experimental

Reagent grade methyl acrylate (Robert Johnson) was distilled under reduced pressure. Dimethylformamide was used as such. α, α' -Azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was recrystallised from methanol (m.p. 102°). Atactic polymethylmethacrylate² with a predominance of syndiotactic sequence, used as template was obtained by polymerizing MMA in dry benzene ([MMA]=6.92 M) under nitrogen at 60° using [AIBN] (0.01 M) as initiator. Its viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) was determined in benzene at 30° using the following relationship³,

$$[\eta] = 8.35 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_v^{0.78}$$

and was found to be 110100. When benzene was replaced by a chain transfer promoting solvent (viz. toluene), polymethyl methacrylate of low molecular weights were obtained. The sample solution containing MA, PMMA, AIBN and DMF was flushed with nitrogen in glass ampoules (6 ml) made of borosilicate glass. The ampoules were then placed in a thermostat (30 ± 0.1°) and the sample was irradiated by a Phillips high pressure mercury lamp (125 W) at 25 cm, light wavelength using 440 nm interference throughout the work. The experiment was terminated after 270 min and the content was poured into a large amount of methanol containing hydroquinone

to precipitate the polymer. The resulting polymer was then purified by reprecipitation and dried in a vacuum oven. The template and daughter polymers were separated by refluxing with benzene. In spite of best efforts, we could not carry out the complete separation. The weight of daughter polymer was used to calculate the percent conversion. The rate of polymerization (R_p) was calculated from the slope of the plot of percent conversion versus time (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plots between percent conversion vs time for the template photo-polymerization of MA: (○) 0.00, (◻) 0.35, (●) 0.40, (△) 0.50, (◻) 0.60, (■) 0.80, (⊗) 0.85 and (⊙) 0.95 base \bar{M} ; [AIBN] = 3.04×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.80 mol dm⁻², temp. = 30°, time = 270 min.

The intrinsic viscosity of daughter polymers, determined in benzene at 30° with an Ubbelohde viscometer, was used to calculate the viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) using the relationship⁴,

$$[\eta] = 4.5 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_v^{0.78}$$

Results and Discussion

Viscosity measurement : In order to investigate complexation between at-PMMA and PMA, the polymers were separately dissolved in dimethyl formamide and mixed just before the measurements. The viscosity measurement was carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The change in reduced viscosity $\eta_{red} = (\eta_{sp}/C)$ of the mixture of at-PMMA and PMA in DMF as a function of composition is shown in Fig. 2. The minimum in both cases lay at a percent by weight of

Fig. 2. Plot between η_{sp}/C and percentage [template]; Temp. = 30° .

at-PMMA corresponding to a 1 : 1 base molar ratio. The rapid drop of η_{red} within 8 min down to a level that examined constant signifies that complexation was very fast and virtually completed in 8 min. Early reports⁶ regarding complete complex formation in template polymerization, also showed that the time required for complete complex formation is generally 10–20 min.

Effects of concentration of the template : The influence of [template] upon the polymerization of methylacrylate, was investigated by comparing the initial rate of polymerization in absence (blank polymerization) and in presence of varying [at-PMMA] from 0.35 to 0.95 M base and the results are compiled in Table 1. The influence of [template] is expressed as the relative rate of polymerization (V_R), defined as

$$V_R = \frac{\text{Rate of template system}}{\text{Rate of the blank system}}$$

A study of Table 1 reveals that the polymerization rate still increases with increasing template concentration above the critical concentration (C^*), i.e. the concentration above which the solution possesses a homogeneous segmental distributions, but the effects is less pronounced and the polymerization rate reaches a constant value. In this case the template

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [Syn-PMMA] ON PHOTO-TEMPLATE POLYMERIZATION OF METHYL ACRYLATE

[AIBN] = 3.04×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.80 mol dm⁻³, Time = 270 min, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.01^\circ$, [Syn-PMMA] $\bar{M}_v = 110100$, Uv-radiation = 440 nm

[Syn-PMMA] base M	$R_p \times 10^6$ mol dm ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹	V_R	\bar{M}_v daughter polymer
0.00	2.45	0.00	67 510
0.35	5.72	1.40	—
0.40	7.35	3.00	70 820
0.50	10.29	4.20	74 200
0.60	12.87	5.25	81 060
0.80	17.16	7.00	91 640
0.85	17.16	7.00	—
0.95	17.26	7.04	92 370

polymerization will take place only when the growing oligomers, created in bulk solution, can be complexed with template. Since complexation is a cooperative process, the oligomer should attain a maximum critical chain length before it gets attached to the template and propagation proceeds by reaction with monomer from the surrounding solution. This will be called type-II or 'picked up mechanism'.

Table 1 further shows that as the concentration of template increased, \bar{M}_v of daughter polymer also increases (linear plot not shown). However, the maximum \bar{M}_v is 92370 which is low in comparison to that of template. This might be due to chain transfer reaction of template as a result of which complete separation could not be achieved. A study of Table 2 shows the influence of viscosity average molecular weight of template on V_R and \bar{M}_v of daughter polymers. It is clear that the V_R and \bar{M}_v of the daughter polymer (Fig. 3) increases with [template], V_R maximum is noted with the template of $\bar{M}_v = 110100$, which decreases as \bar{M}_v of the template decreases as expected for template polymerization.

Fig 3 Plots between relative rate of polymerization, average viscosity, molecular weight and intrinsic viscosity.

Effect of monomer concentration : The effect of the [monomer] upon the polymerization rate was

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF Syn-PMMA OF DIFFERENT MOLECULAR WEIGHT ON THE PHOTO-TEMPLATE POLYMERIZATION OF METHYL ACRYLATE

[AIBN] = 3.04×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.80 mol dm⁻³, Time = 270 min, Temp = $30 \pm 0.01^\circ$, Uv-radiation = 440 nm

Syn-PMMA	\bar{M}_v	R_p $\times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	\bar{V}_R	\bar{M}_v polymer
syn-PMMA-1	77 650	6.99	2.85	71 948
syn-PMMA-2	85 750	9.18	3.74	80 640
syn-PMMA-3	100 010	12.29	5.01	89 340
syn-PMMA-4	110 100	17.16	7.00	91 640

investigated. The linearity of the plot (not shown) between \bar{V}_R and [MA], shows that oligomers created in solution are adsorbed by the template sites thus mechanism-II operates in the present system, because in case of mechanism-I, the curve would be concave⁶.

Effect of concentration of initiator : The influence of [AIBN] on the polymerization, has been studied and the order of reaction with respect to AIBN, calculated from the linear plot of log R_p vs log [AIBN] (not shown) is 0.50.

Effect of temperature : The overall energy of activation (ΔE) in the presence and absence of PMMA (template), calculated from Arrhenius plot, was found to be 84 and 115 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The decrease in the overall activation energy in the presence of template is possible due to an increase in activation energy of termination. It is possible that a strongly hindered segmental mobility of radical chains, which are observed on PMMA, enhances the apparent activation energy of the termination reaction. Similarly, in the case of the polymerization of methylmethacrylate Gons *et al.*⁷ reported the termination rate constant to be 82 times smaller in presence of added poly(MMA) than that in the absence of polymer.

Effect of analogue of template : In order to certain that the influence is due to the polymeric character of the template, the rate was also determined by adding a molecular analogue of PMMA,

viz. ethyl propionate. In the presence of 0.8 mol dm⁻³ ethyl propionate, the polymerization rate at 60° is found to be identical as the rate of polymerization found in the presence of poly(methylmethacrylate). The result shows that the rate of polymerization remains unaffected⁸ hence the system follows mechanism-II, because in case of mechanism-I, the addition of an analogue of the template generally reduces the overall rate of polymerization.

Thus, in the present system the photopolymerization of methylacrylate follows mechanism-II in the presence of poly(methylmethacrylate).

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